

Eyes, hairs and dermatologic antenna in a brain-spinal cord-heart circuit

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Abstract: Neurons within the brain and spinal cord play the role of electronic wires and transform electrical currents. Some of them join to each other and form some circles like the circles within the inductors. These biological inductors couple to neurons within the heart. Heart acts like a generator or battery and produce electrical currents. Also, it plays the role of capacitor and store electrical charges for a short period of time and then enters to the discharge phase. Brain, spinal cord and heart build a resonant circuit in a biological receiver/sender of electromagnetic waves. To exchange these waves with medium, eyes, hairs, melanocytes and dermatologic cells play the role of antennas. These antennas have the main role in diagnosing some diseases like melanoma and other types of cancers. Because, any evolution in cancerous cells has a direct effect on the emitted waves from dermatologic and other biologic antennas. Each biologic antenna separate an special frequency from a general wave from the brain-spinal cord-heart circuit and send an special information to medium. We examine the model by measurement of dermatologic waves before and after external fields. We observe that by increasing external fields, dermatologic waves response and emit more waves to medium. This is because that they take external waves, transform to the brain-spinal cord-heart circuit, obtain its response and send new waves to medium. We also obtain very interesting results about radiation of light from eyes. We cover eyes and put other dermatologic antenna in front of sun or other lighting lamps. We take a video of eyes and detect some emitted lights from their cells. This occurs, because the circuit of brain-spinal cord-heart take some signals from dermatologic antenna, analyze them, transfer their information to eye's optical cells and force them to send some waves.

I. Introduction

Up to day, many scientists have tried to understand the origin of dermatologic waves and their relation with various types of diseases like melanoma. To this aim, they have explored the origin of electrical currents within the biological

systems. For example, some researchers have shown that bacterial and viral DNAs could emit some types of waves [1,2]. This is because that a DNA has been constructed from electrical charges and consequently, by any motion of a DNA, its charges move and some electrical currents are emerged. These currents are the origin of DNA waves within the cells [3]. These DNA waves are transmitted by some wires which are called neurons. These neurons join to each other and form nervous system. This system has three main parts. 1. Brain 2. Spinal cord and 3. Little brain on the heart. Brain has been known as a center of voluntary activity which contributes in decision processes and spinal cord has been recognized as a center of non-voluntary activity. However, the role of little brain on the heart has been ignored. This 'little brain' on the heart is comprised of spatially distributed sensory (afferent), interconnecting (local circuit) and motor (adrenergic and cholinergic efferent) neurones that communicate with others in intrathoracic extracardiac ganglia, all under the tonic influence of central neuronal command and circulating catecholamines. Neurones residing from the level of the heart to the insular cortex form temporally dependent reflexes that control overlapping, spatially determined cardiac indices [4,5]. In fact, cardiac function is under the control of the autonomic nervous system, composed by the parasympathetic and sympathetic divisions, which are finely tuned at different hierarchical levels. It has been shown that while a complex regulation occurs in the central nervous system involving the insular cortex, the amygdala and the hypothalamus, a local cardiac regulation also takes place within the heart, driven by an intracardiac nervous system. This complex system consists of a network of ganglionic plexuses and interconnecting ganglions and axons [6]. Now, the question arises that what is the relation between this nervous system and radiated waves from dermatologic diseases like melanoma? We answer this question by proposing a new model which connect dermatologic cells to nervous system. We show that eye, hair and other dermatologic cells play the role of antenna for brain-heart-spinal cord circuit.

Melanoma is one of most dangerous type of skin cancer that develops from the pigment-containing cells known as melanocytes [7,8]. Melanomas are usually caused by DNA damage resulting from exposure of melanocytes [9-12] to ultraviolet light from the sun[13] or some genetic problems [14]. Thus, there is a direct relation between electromagnetic waves and appearance or growth of this disease. To control the progress of this cancer and other dermatologic diseases, we consider the mechanism of exchanged electrical currents between

nervous system and dermatologic cells from one hand and exchanged waves between dermatologic antenna and medium from other hand.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we simulate heart, spinal cord, brain, eye, melanocytes and hair with electronic devices and build a sender/receiver circuit. In section III, we propose a method to take electromagnetic waves of dermatologic antenna. In section IV, we show our results and discuss about probable events during experiments. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Dermatologic antenna in a brain-heart-spinal cord circuit

In this section, we simulate brain, heart and spinal cord with electronic devices and show that dermatologic cells act like the antenna in a receiver or sender of waves. These antennas could help us in controlling some diseases.

To begin, we consider neural circuits within the brain and the spinal cord. In these circuits, neurons act like electronic wires and carry electrochemical signals. By motion of charges, a current is emerged which move along neural circuits. Some circuits have the shape of circle or coil and produce a magnetic field along axis. By joining these circles, some inductors are emerged which interact with each other within the brain and spinal cord. These inductors produce some electromagnetic fields which their frequencies and strengths depend on the values of currents and exchanged electrical charges between neurons. These waves carry main information about evolutions of cells, brain and spinal cord (See Figure 1).

Fig1 : Inductors within the brain and the spinal cord

Another main electronic device in a human/animal's body is the heart. This system acts like the generator and send some electrons and other charges to circuits. In addition, heart acts like a capacitor, take charges from one side, store them for some short period of time and then give them to the circuit from other sides. This is very similar to capacitor which takes charges, store them and then send them to electronic circuit (See Figure 2). Heart as the biological capacitor can unify with the brain and spinal cord as the biological inductor and produce some resonances. This means that these biological capacitor-inductor systems separate special frequencies and produce special waves.

Fig 2: Heart acts like a generator or battery and a Capacitor

The brain-Spinal cord-heart system as the capacitor-inductor circuit could exchange waves with medium. To do this, there are some dermatologic antenna like melanocytes, hairs and eyes. Each of these antennas only receives or sends an special frequency of waves (See Figure 3). We can write:

$$F(t, \Omega^t) = \sum P_n G_n(t_n, \Omega_n) \quad (1)$$

Where F is the function of general wave which is produced by the brain-Spinal cord-heart system and G_n are the function of micro waves which construct that general wave. Also, P_n is the probability for producing each micro wave. On the other hand, Ω^t and Ω_n are frequencies of general wave and microwaves respectively. Each biological antenna take a micro wave from medium and transform it to central nervous system. These waves are join to each other and produce a total current which moves along the brain-Spinal cord-heart system.

Fig 3: Melanocytes, hairs and eyes act like the antenna

A collection of biological antennas, heart, brain and spinal cord form the electronic circuit of human/animal's body (See Figure 4). This system can take some waves from medium, analyze them and send to cells. Thus, any wave can have a direct effect on the life of creatures. Also, human/animal's body could send some waves to medium through its antenna which carry main information about its evolutions. For example, if a melanoma occurs, radiated waves of biological antenna change. Because, in these conditions, some melanocytes lose their connections with the brain-Spinal cord-heart and the strength of frequency of general wave change. We have:

$$F_{\text{cancer}}(t, \Omega^t) = \sum P_n G_n(t_n, \Omega_n) - \sum P_m G_m(t_m, \Omega_m) \quad (2)$$

Where n is the index related to healthy cells and m is the index related to cancerous cells. Also, F_{cancer} is the general wave function of a cancer patient and Ω^t is its frequency. Comparing signals of health parts of body with cancerous ones, we can obtain the values of wavefunctions related to cancerous cells. These functions help us to consider amount of growth of cancerous cells.

Fig 4 : A similarity between heart-brain-spinal cord and dermatologic antenna with an electrical circuit

III. Material and method

We can examine the model by taking waves from eye, hair and other dermatologic antenna. To this aim, we need to below materials:

1. Sunlight or lamps with lights from different colors.
2. Some barriers which each of them remove some frequencies
3. Graphene sheet

4. magnetic diode/detector
5. Scopes like Radio-SkyPipe or Oscilloscope
6. Wires
7. Magnets
8. Camera

The method for examining the model is as follows

1. We put a graphene sheet including some pentagonal and heptagonal molecules on dermatologic antenna. Differences in electrical charges between hexagonal and pentagonal molecules lead to the motion of free electrons along graphene sheet and emergence of a current. Any external field can cause to increasing this current which could be observed on the scope.
2. Instead of graphene sheet, we can use of a magnetic diode or a detector. We can build this detector by putting two magnets in two sites of a metal which produce two opposite magnetic fields. Electrons between these fields, have opposite directions and are paired. Any external field can cause to the break of these pair and emergence of a current along metal.
3. We connect graphene sheet or magnetic detectors to an scope
4. We put a sunscreen in front of sunlight and measure currents which are emerged by dermatologic waves in the absence of sun light.
5. We remove sunscreen and measure currents which are emerged by dermatologic waves emitted from dermatologic antennas in the presence of sun light (See Figure 5).
6. We cover an eye by a sunscreen and put a camera like a camera of mobile on the eye and take a video. We observe radiated light from eyes.

Fig 5 : A method for taking waves from dermatologic antenna

IV. Results

Our experiments have below results:

1. Before external radiations like sun light radiations, we can detect some emitted waves from dermatologic antennas (See Figure 6).
2. Dermatologic antenna are in fact parts of a the brain-spinal cord heart. They separate some microwaves from a general wave and send it to medium. By analyzing these waves, we can predict evolutions of human's body.
3. After external radiations, like sun light radiations, we can detect more emitted waves from dermatologic waves. Because, in these conditions, first, dermatologic antenna take waves of medium and transform it to the brain-spinal cord –heart circuit. This system, analyzes external waves and

responses. This response can cause to an increase in biological currents within the spinal cord or brain and sending some extra currents towards eyes, hairs and other dermatologic antennas. Consequently, these antenna send some waves to medium in response to received waves (See Figure 7).

4. By increasing radiations of sun or any external sources, more evolutions are occurred in human/animal's body and in response, more waves are emitted by dermatologic antenna (See figure 8).
5. In addition, a brain-spinal cord-heart can send some signals to eye's cells and force them to act reverse to their normal action during vision. We can detect some radiated lights from eyes in front of sun light or other lighting devices, while, we cover head in front of sun (See Figure 9).

Fig 6: Measured currents from dermatologic antenna which are taken by Radio-SkyPipe before sunlight radiation

Fig 7: Electromagnetic waves from dermatologic antenna which are observed by Radio-SkyPipe after sunlight radiation

Fig 8: Increasing dermatologic waves by increasing lump or sunlight waves. Light Blue, red, green and dark blue are corresponded to external currents with $I = 200, 400, 800$ and 1000 mA observed by Radio-SkyPipe.

Fig 9: Radiated light from an eye

V. Conclusion

In this research, we have shown that brain, spinal cord and heart form an electronic circuit and eyes, hairs and dermatologic cells play the role of their antenna. To this aim, we have considered neural circuits within the brain and spinal cords and shown that some of them build circles of inductors. These circuits connect to neural circuits within the heart. Heart's neurons form a generator and a capacitor. A collection of brain-spinal cord and heart build a

resonant circuit similar to the resonant circuit of capacitor-inductor. This circuit produce a general current which divide to micro currents. These micro currents are taken by eyes, hairs, melanocytes and other dermatologic cells. These cells act like the receiver or sender antenna and exchange waves with medium. By analyzing radiated waves from biological antenna, we can predict evolutions in human/animal's body. We have examined model by analyzing radiated waves from dermatologic antenna. We have observed that dermatologic antenna response to the waves of medium and help us to predict evolutions of cells. We can use of these antenna in imaging and curing some diseases like cancers. We also show that a brain-spinal cord-heart can force to eye's cells and cause to radiation of light. This may have main application in imaging.

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